

Wax Moth Larvae: From Nuisome Parasites to Hope for Ecosystem Rescue

Quan-Hoang Vuong

17-12-2023

* * * * *

This short article provides information about a lesson on the value of biodiversity in an ecosystem currently suffering severe damage due to human socio-economic activities [1].

The story begins with the highly characteristic theory of serendipity [2], as narrated by the author Sandy Ong in ASBMB Today [3]. One gloomy spring morning in 2012, Federica Bertocchini, a developmental biologist, was tending to beehives near her home in Santander, on the beautiful northern coast of Spain. One of the beehives was being disturbed by a swarm of parasitic caterpillars. Among these pesky parasites were the larvae of wax moths, known for their voracious and destructive appetite.

Bertocchini collected the caterpillars, put them in a plastic bag, and continued with her beekeeping duties. When she took out the bag a few hours later, she noticed something strange: small holes had appeared in the bag.

The scientist's curiosity was piqued, in line with the principle of serendipity [2], and immediately raised important questions:

Had these caterpillars simply bitten through the plastic bag, or had they altered its chemical structure?

Surprisingly, quick experiments in her laboratory confirmed that a component in the caterpillars' saliva had degraded the plastic bag.

Since then, a new research program began for Bertocchini.

Federica Bertocchini founded the company Plasticentropy — one of several startups and research groups that have sprouted in recent years to explore ways of recycling plastic in a biologically friendly manner. This bio-based recycling method could provide more efficient and environmentally friendly solutions than some of the current recycling methods that are facing challenges and demanding extensive conditions for implementation [4].

Today, there are hundreds of research groups worldwide, comprising thousands of scientists, all pursuing enzyme-based techniques for plastic recycling. The desire to find solutions that mimic ecosystem processes has led today's scientists to scour landfills, junkyards, and plastic-polluted areas in search of microorganisms capable of breaking down plastic into its constituent parts.

By isolating these bacteria and enhancing their plastic-degrading abilities in the lab, scientists hope to find more effective ways to separate the chemical components of plastic. These recovered materials can then be reused to produce new materials, creating a never-ending recycling loop.

While the search for suitable microorganisms and enzymes for this task is just the first step, the world has already recognized that biologically based recycling is an answer to environmental pollution. Earth's ecosystem holds an immensely valuable "ecosystem service" that provides a biological toolkit to combat the global plastic waste crisis threatening ecosystems worldwide.

The lesson in creative potential when seeking solutions from nature not only rekindles hope for saving ecosystems but also prompts human thinking towards creating humane values oriented towards harmony with the natural world. Ultimately, it is still the ecosystem itself that self-rescues, with its intricately woven and highly sophisticated hidden capabilities.

It turns out that the best thing human values can probably do is to restrain themselves from further damaging their own living environment, after all, as Kingfisher's humor ultimately proves [5].

References

- [1] Vuong, Q. H., & Nguyen, M. H. (2024). Kingfisher: Contemplating the connection between nature and humans through science, art, literature and live experiences. *Pacific Conservation Biology*. <https://doi.org/10.1071/PC23044>

- [2] Vuong, Q. H. (2022). *A New Theory of Serendipity: Nature, Emergence and Mechanism*. Berlin, Germany: De Gruyter. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0C5C4LPF1>
- [3] Ong, S. (2023). The living things that feast on plastic. <https://www.asbmb.org/asbmb-today/science/091023/the-living-things-that-feast-on-plastic>
- [4] Nguyen, M. H., & Jones, T. E. (2022). Building eco-surplus culture among urban residents as a novel strategy to improve finance for conservation in protected areas. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 9(1), 426. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-022-01441-9>
- [5] Vuong, Q. H. (2022). *The Kingfisher Story Collection*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0BG2NNHY6>